

The need for tailored approaches in Arctic economic development to promote sustainability and social inclusion

POLICY BRIEF

The socio-cultural effects of economic activities in the Arctic and Alpine regions underscore the need for tailored, inclusive development strategies that balance economic growth, environmental sustainability, social inclusion, and cultural preservation. Policies that prioritize these values, as identified by local and indigenous communities, can enhance quality of life and foster resilient, thriving societies. This policy brief calls for collaborative efforts to ensure sustainable and equitable development in both regions.

The European Arctic is seeing increased activity in fish farming, forestry, mining, tourism, and indigenous activities like reindeer husbandry and hunting¹. Industry growth is driven by global population growth, rising living standards, and technological advancements, coupled with the shift towards carbon-neutral societies, increasing the demand for minerals for renewable energy technologies².

While these developments offer economic opportunities, they also pose significant environmental, social, and cultural impacts, particularly on local and indigenous communities whose livelihoods are vulnerable to these changes. ArcticHubs project examines these developments, focusing on industry's socio-cultural effects, Social License to Operate (SLO), and emphasizing the need for sustainable resource utilization to protect fragile

RECOMMENDATIONS

- Redefine development and move towards post-growth frameworks, and prioritize social and ecological wellbeing
- Diversify economic activities and invest in sustainable and just enterprises
- Promote transparent and inclusive processes for all stakeholders
- Leverage local and indigenous knowledge
- Adapt the Social License to Operate to other industries

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Arctic ecosystems and communities. Comparing the Arctic with Austria and Italy, which share similar harsh climates and natural resource dependencies but are further along in development, provides valuable insights³. As such, this policy brief highlights findings on socio-cultural effects and SLO in Arctic industries, lessons from the Alpine region, and recommends sustainable, inclusive development policies.

KEY FINDINGS

ECONOMIC STRUCTURE AND DIVERSIFICATION

The Arctic region exhibits a high dependence on single industries (e.g., mining, fishing, forestry), resulting in economic vulnerabilities.

The Alpine region, with its more diversified economy, serves as a learning model for economic resilience and adaptability.

SOCIO-CULTURAL IMPACTS

Arctic Region: Indigenous communities face significant socio-cultural disruptions due to industrial expansion. Traditional livelihoods such as reindeer herding are threatened by land exploitation and environmental degradation.

Alpine Region: Historical industrial activities have shaped the socio-cultural landscape, with current efforts focusing on preserving cultural heritage and promoting sustainable tourism.

ENVIRONMENTAL SUSTAINABILITY

Both regions face environmental challenges, but the Arctic's fragile ecosystems are particularly susceptible to industrial activities. Stronger environmental protections are essential to mitigate these impacts.

In the Alpine region, adaptive management practices are crucial for balancing economic activities with environmental conservation.

COMMUNITY INVOLVEMENT AND DECISION-MAKING

Effective development requires inclusive decision-making processes that involve local communities and respect indigenous rights.

There is a need for greater transparency and collaboration between stakeholders to ensure that development projects align with local socio-cultural values and environmental sustainability goals

BALANCING COMMUNITY INTEREST: SOCIAL LICENSE TO OPERATE (SLO)

SLO concept is relevant to the aquaculture industry, which, like mining, impacts local areas. Both industries face challenges such as environmental effects, impacts on other industries, leisure activities, and infrastructure, but they also generate substantial economic benefits at the industry level.

In forestry, SLO is significantly influenced by ownership structure, with much of the forest land owned by local communities. SLO is granted by a broader group of stakeholders who value the ecosystem services provided by forests, including recreational opportunities, visual landscape quality, and climate regulation. Similarly, tourism in the Arctic exemplifies the SLO concept, where profitability, community dependence, and the balance of various important elements and trade-offs are evident⁴.

POLICY RECOMMENDATIONS IN DETAIL

Redefine development

Move away from development models that prioritize economic growth above all else and embrace "post-growth" frameworks like degrowth and doughnut economics, which center on social and ecological well-being. Unregulated economic expansion, particularly when influenced by external interests, can undermine the long-term sustainability of the Arctic and its communities, especially Indigenous groups. A fundamental reassessment of current economic strategies and the prevailing "business as usual" mindset is essential to ensure lasting stability and resilience. Additionally, it is crucial to prevent terms like sustainability and green transition from being exploited as mere justifications for further industrial expansion⁵.

Diversify Economic Activities

Invest in sustainable tourism, just renewable energy, and local entrepreneurship to create diverse economic opportunities. Support small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) and traditional industries to strengthen local economies. Diversification of economic activities would help local communities avoid overreliance on single extractive industries, shielding them from the vulnerabilities of boom-and-bust cycles. However, new projects and economic activities should undergo rigorous environmental and social impact assessments to ensure they do not harm local ecosystems or cultural sites.

...balance among economic development, environmental sustainability, social inclusion and cultural preservation are crucial for fostering healthy and thriving communities in Arctic and Alpine regions

Promote transparent and Inclusive processes

Transparent and inclusive decision-making processes are essential, ensuring that all stakeholders are involved at every level. Businesses and policymakers must actively listen to local voices to foster trust and establish sustainable partnerships. Engaging local communities early in project development helps cultivate a sense of ownership. Scholars advocate for approaches like deliberative democracy, meta-consensus, and structured disagreement, which create spaces for stakeholders to express concerns and explore solutions. The goal is not necessarily to reach agreements but to enhance mutual understanding and trust. For instance, in Inari, local stakeholders co-developed a forest management toolkit with shared principles to reduce procurement risks and mitigate negative impacts, benefiting reindeer husbandry⁵.

Leverage Local Knowledge

Integrating local knowledge and respecting Indigenous rights are vital for sustainable practices. Tools like Public Participation GIS (PPGIS) help ensure that local and Indigenous communities actively contribute to

planning, zoning, and reindeer husbandry strategies. For example, RenGIS—a specialized tool for knowledge co-production—combines traditional knowledge from reindeer herding communities with updated data on land use, including mining and forestry. This system tracks reindeer movements, routes, and grazing areas, providing crucial insights for husbandry planning. Additionally, the development of an automated unmanned forestry machine supports small-scale, targeted forestry operations, aiming to minimize negative impacts on reindeer husbandry and other land uses. Special attention is given to preserving lichens during soil scarification and planting. However, while technological innovations offer potential benefits, they are not standalone solutions. Their implementation must follow ethical guidelines, prioritizing the needs and data rights of local and Indigenous communities over purely industrial interests⁵.

Adapt SLO to other industries

Models and general elements of SLO developed for mining can be applied to other industries. However, apparent contextual differences require an aggregation of the SLO elements. Modelling and measuring relationships is not meaningful on the general level and is context-dependent. In addition, acquiring SLO should favor qualitative methods for further research due to the Arctic's sparse population and distinct local communities⁴.

HOW DID WE DO IT?

The policy recommendations were drawn from the results of 69 in-depth expert interviews and 1 Arctic level and 8 locally focused surveys using Q-method with a total of 158 respondents.

We analyzed perspectives of local stakeholders and indigenous peoples to gain insights on the effects of economic activities on the socioeconomic and cultural aspects. On the other hand, SLO investigated sustainability and corporate social responsibility reports to determine whether the concept of SLO can be implemented in the forestry, fish farming and tourism industries

TERMINOLOGIES

SLO – Affected communities' perception of acceptance of the industry.

Q-method - Mixed qualitative and quantitative method to study perspectives in a systematic and replicable manner.

STUDY SITES

- | | | |
|--------------|------------------------|--------------------|
| 1. Kemi | 7. Gran Sameby | 12. Egersund |
| 2. Kemijärvi | 8. Gällivare | 13. Westfjords |
| 3. Inari | 9. Kautokeino-Kvalsund | 14. Nuup Kangerlua |
| 4. Kittilä | 10. Varangerfjord | 15. Suđuroy |
| 5. Jokkmokk | 11. Svalbard | |
| 6. Malå | | |

Learning cases

- 18. Ennstaler Alpen
- 19. Liezen
- 20. Alagna Valsesia
- 21. Germanasca Valley

ArcticHubs project location

Blue: fish farming, green: forestry, purple: tourism, orange: mining, yellow: indigenous activities.

Black circles are local Q-study sites and all hubs are included in Arctic level Q-study

MORE INFORMATION

This policy brief was produced as part of the Arctichubs project. A full report on the sociocultural effects is available in <https://projects.luke.fi/arctichubs/> or access our ArcticHubs videobox series hosted at BOKU YouTube channel by scanning the QR code below, or send a message to our contact persons:

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PHOTOS

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